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Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
European Research Infrastructure Consortium

Training at CESSDA

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European Diversity of CESSDA SPs

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

3 primary communities:

- Data producers
- Data users
- Professionals at Service Providers

-> Train the research community throughout the research lifecycle.

■ **Members** 16 +1
■ **Partners**

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Expert tour guide on Data Management

About this expert tour guide

This tour guide aims to put social scientists like yourself at the heart of making their research data findable, sustainably accessible and (re)usable.

You will be guided by European experts who are - on a daily basis - busy ensuring long-term access to valuable social science datasets, available for discovery and reuse at one of the 15 CESSDA social science data archives. With this guide and training events throughout Europe, we want to accompany and inspire you in your travels through the research data lifecycle.

cessda.eu/DMGuide

8 content partners.

DANS (NL) leading the project.

4 testing partners.

Adapt your Data Management Plan

A list of Data Management Questions based on the Expert Tour Guide on Data Management

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Chapters in the tour guide on Data Management

Local diversity

Expert tips

*Presentations
and exercises*

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Future events and work

RDM Expert Tour Guide: [Train the Trainers Workshop](#) / 12 – 13 April / Ljubljana, Slovenia

Local RMD training events

CESSDA Workshop: Exploring data in Europe - with a focus on European attitudes and Value / 29 May / Prague, Czech Republic

Data Discovery workshop at 3 summer schools

CESSDA Data Catalogue

CESSDA Knowledge Platform

Training

Training focuses on 'train the trainers' and new modes of sharing expertise

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